

PEDAGOGICAL SYSTEM OF IMPROVING COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCES IN STUDENTS BASED ON INTEGRATIVE EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. *It is desirable to build opportunities for students to develop communicative competences on the basis of a competent approach and person-oriented teaching. In order to implement a competent approach, which is important in the teaching process, its components are the relationship between learning and teaching.*

Keywords: *pedagogy of reserve opportunities, conceptual, competent approach, person-oriented, communicative competence, competent approach.*

Analyzing modern educational concepts and comparing them with the goals of communication skills in the higher education system, we determined the conceptual basis of improving the quality of education in students based on integrative educational technology. As a first approach, we highlight the *pedagogy of spare capacity*, since it is considered the main one in all integrative teaching methods [see Table 2.1].

G.K.Lozanov emphasizes that the reserves of the human psyche are very large, and we do not set the task of repeating the integrative method proposed by him, on the contrary, we base the educational process in his theory on the basis of the pedagogy of reserve opportunities, which allows teaching on the basis of integrative educational technology. we suggest using the given aspects. As an option for such training, we used the theory and technology of effective pedagogy, which is based on the pedagogy of reserve opportunities and helps to reveal leading reserves of teaching in the pedagogical process; (See Table 2.1):

2.1-table.

Conceptual foundations of increasing educational efficiency

№	Self-improvement	Opportunities
1.	It is related to the identification of difficulties encountered in the implementation of educational activities and the training of necessary skills that help to overcome these difficulties.	The process of training and improving skills is based on the principle of compatibility with nature. necessary internal reserves (memory, imagination, etc.) should be developed first.
2.	It is related to the activation of intellectual reserves of students during the teaching period	Using active methods of teaching, such as training, games, problem solving; is carried out at the expense of students' independent creative activity, team and pair cooperation.
3.	The attitude of the student to the educational process, his motivation is necessary	The formation of internal positive motivation helps to activate educational activities.

4.	Communicativeness, empathy, emotional expressiveness	It is the formation of a number of qualities of a person necessary for action.
5.	Increasing the effectiveness of the educational process is related to the organization of understanding the initial educational material	Mastering the learning material is related to the transition from its first presentation and the peculiarities of perception causing difficulties to be eliminated.

The use of the listed resources significantly activates the pedagogical process without causing additional mental or physical fatigue at the expense of the available opportunities in teaching. The pedagogy of reserve possibilities applies to all types of training and affects them in a complex way.

The technology of bringing out the pedagogy of reserve opportunities in the educational process is based on its individualization, because it is necessary to take into account the unique characteristics of each student and develop the technology of forming and improving the necessary components.

It is the relationship between teaching and learning that implements a competent approach that is important in the teaching process. It is desirable to build these relationships (pedagogical interactions) on the basis of person-oriented teaching. The valuable aspect of the developed approach is, first of all, the socialization of the pedagogical process.

Person-oriented education is considered a natural system and is formed taking into account the student's unique personal development, his unique abilities and psychological orientations. Person-oriented technology has been developed since 1999 on the basis of integration of pedagogical ideas, personal pedagogical experience and conducted experiments.

According to Sh.Sharipov, the term "person-oriented education" refers to the personal interests and needs of students. In this case, the main goal is to direct the content of education in accordance with the interests of the student, to support his interests and abilities.

VV Serikov says that the meaning of the person-oriented approach is to create conditions for the personal tasks of the student, his universal personal abilities: motivation, creativity, self-expression, reflection, etc.

In the process of person-oriented education, the student is the main participant of the entire educational process, an independent learning subject with equal rights to the teacher, and the teacher is not only a "source of information" and a "controller", but also more is also a facilitator, supporter, motivator and diagnostician for student personality development.

The personality of the student is at the center of education with his individual characteristics, age-related characteristics, needs to maximize his potential. This type of teaching creates optimal conditions for the emergence and development of a student's personality; will consist of "supporting self-determination and self-expression through education". The learning process is focused on the abilities of the student's personality, which develops during the teaching process and is based on the student's interests, as well as taking into account the abilities of personal growth and individual knowledge to learn the knowledge of academic subjects more easily. ensures mastery. The founder of this concept, I.S.Yakimanskaya, distinguishes between the teaching process and the learning process. Being the subject of knowledge activity, the student

creates his subjective experience through educational activity, as a result of which the following are the different aspects of the educational technology under consideration:

change of content and form of communication: communication between teacher and student;

orientation to the dynamics of individual development of each subject in education and creating conditions for him to bring out his own development process;

actively encourage the student to carry out valuable educational activities;

maximum use of experiences in the family, social circles and similar life activities and enriching it by introducing components of other cultures, values, characteristics of national identity and so on.

In these respects, it is consistent with the goal of modern communicative ability and its formation. The increase in communication experience enriches the development of the student's intercultural communication and his subjective experiences in life activities.

Organization of a person-oriented approach creates conditions for increasing the effectiveness of teaching communicative abilities of students based on intensive educational technology.

Having completed the analysis of theoretical approaches to the problem of improving the quality of teaching communicative competence based on intensive educational technology, we believe that it is necessary to distinguish three theoretical directions: the first is the competent approach, which is the modern higher education system and is the main direction in science. As the second direction, we chose a person-oriented approach as a lever that allows us to effectively organize the process of formation of basic competencies. As the third direction, we chose the pedagogy of reserve opportunities, because it allows to significantly increase the level of manifestation of a number of cognitive and social skills that appear as the main competencies in the formation of readiness to teach English on the basis of intensive educational technology.

REFERENCES

1. Oliy ta'lim tizimini yanada takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining PQ-2909-son Qarori. 2017 yil 20 aprel.

2. Lozanov G. Suggestopaedia – Desuggestive Teaching Communicative Method on the Level of the Hidden Reserves of the Human Mind. – Vienna: International Centre for Desuggestology, 2005. – 140 p.

3. Карпова О.Л. Педагогическая концепция содействия развитию самообразовательной деятельности студентов вуза. Монография – Челябинск: УралГУФК, 2009. – 310 с.

4. Сериков В. В. Личностно ориентированное образование // Педагогика. – М., 1994. – № 5. – С. 16-21.

5. Sharipov Sh.S. O'quvchilar kasbiy ijodkorligi uzviyligini ta'minlashning nazariyasi va amaliyoti.: Avtoref. dis. ... ped. fan. dok. – T., 2012. – 46 b.

6. Якиманская И. С. Личностно ориентированное обучение в современной школе. – М., 1996. – С. 24-25.